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**From Individual Reason to Collective Instinct:
Crowd Psychology in Lord of the Flies**

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The novel " Lord of the Flies" and the psychology of the masses

The novel *The Lord of the Flies* by William Golding is one of the most prominent literary works that dealt with human nature and the behavior of individuals within groups. The novel tells the story of a group of boys stranded on a remote island after their plane crashes, where they initially try to build an organized society, but soon slide into chaos and violence.

The events of the novel can be connected with the ideas of the book *The Crowd: a Study of the Popular Mind* by The Thinker Gustave Le Bon, who sees that when an individual becomes part of a crowd or a group he loses an aspect of his independent personality and is subject to the influence of collective feelings. Le Bon asserts that audiences tend to act emotionally and irrationally, and that psychological contagion causes thoughts and behaviors to spread rapidly among group members.

This is clearly manifested in the novel by the transformation of the boys from rule-abiding children into an impulsive, violent collective under the leadership of Jack. The sense of belonging to the collective and the desire for power led to a decline in individual and moral thinking, which corresponds to Le Bon's analysis of the behavior of the masses. The fear of the "beast" in the novel also serves as an example of how irrational beliefs spread within the collective until they become a reality acceptable to everyone.

The Lord of the Flies thus provides a practical literary embodiment of many of the ideas put forward by Le Bon in his book *The Psychology of the masses*, showing how collective pressures and psychological infection can influence the behavior of individuals and guide their decisions away from rational thinking. Through this interconnection of literature and Social Psychology, the novel reveals the mechanisms that make groups vulnerable to fear, intolerance and violence, making it an important literary model for understanding the psychology of the masses and their transformations in various social contexts.